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Multiband imaging of 14 medeival fragments.

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Abbreviations

IR	Infrared (ca. 700–1100 nm)
IRR	Infrared reflectance
IRRFC	Infrared-reflected false-colour
MBI	Multiband imaging
UV	Ultraviolet (ca. 200–400 nm)
UVL	Ultraviolet luminescence
UVR	Ultraviolet reflectance
UVRFC	Ultraviolet-reflected false-colour
VIS	Visible (ca. 400–700 nm)

Objects description

Fragments from medieval manuscripts selected by the user group of the IPERION HS project MoMNopSaF. 14 pages (parchment with handwritten text and illuminations) were imaged. All fragments are searchable in the digital MPO database of the National Archives. The selection of fragments of MoMNopSaF was further modified after this imaging was performed resulting in 9635 “list with yellow line” and 4602 “Blue o” being excluded from the final selection, while 25621 “Calendar with blue text” was added (not included in multiband imaging, a VIS image provided by the National Archives is added last in the appendix to allow overview of all fragments in MoMNopSaF).

Object nr	Page description
3814	"Illumination, Jesus on cross"
4602	"Blue p initial"
4602	"Blue o initial"
6638	"Bright yellow J"
7285	"Music notes, red and black cadels"
7285	"Music notes, red and black cadels"
9451	"Green and red initials"
9635	"List with yellow line"
9635	"Music notes, marked Finland"
9635	"Reds and greens"
10156	"Black flourishes with face"
10411	"Initial S with dots"
26692	"P and U"
26692	"Jesus on cross"
25621	"Calendar with blue text" (<i>n.b. not included in multiband imaging</i>)

Purpose

Multiband imaging (VIS, IRR, UVL, UVR, IRRFC, UVRFC) was performed for documentation and to visualize the pigment palette of the selected fragments in preparation for further analyses within the project MoMNopSaF.

Comments on set-up

All images were captured with the objects placed horizontally with the camera mounted above. The objects were placed on a black paper background. The camera was positioned circa 100 cm above the object and two light sources were placed on opposite sides with approximately a 45-degree angle towards the object. Some fragments could not be positioned entirely flat and were mounted appropriately by staff at Riksarkivet. Weight bags were used to flatten the fragments and stabilize the set-up, visible in some images.

Comments on standardisation and post processing

The Heritage Laboratory follow the guidelines for multiband imaging as presented in the user manual that was developed by the British Museum during the EU-funded CHARISMA project¹. The manual details practices to improve the reproducibility of the method between users and institutions, including the use of specific standards. For post processing Nip2 is a graphical interface for the image processing system VIPS that is open-source and can be downloaded free of charge². Nip2 has many features; for example, it can

utilize standards to colour calibrate and correct for spatial inhomogeneities of the light source. The processing and use of Nip2 is described in detail in the manual. Every object and on-site photography setup provide different circumstances and challenges, therefore some variation in set-up between sessions may occur.

Image types

Image	Lightsource	Filter	Purpose
VIS	VIS (flash)	VIS	Standard image.
IRR	IR (flash)	IR	IR reflection upon illumination by IR light. Useful to study underdrawings in paintings. Many materials such as organic dyes and binders become transparent under these conditions.
UVL	UV	VIS	Luminescence in the VIS region upon illumination by UV light. Useful to visualize organic binders and dyes. Some inorganic materials also have luminescent properties, e.g. zinc oxide.
UVR	UV	UV	UV reflection upon illumination by UV light. Useful to visualize coatings and varnishes.
IRRFC			In IRRFC the red channel from IRR is combined with the red and green channel from the VIS image. Some pigments have characteristic colour changes.
UVRFC			In UVRFC the blue channel from UVR is combined with the green and blue channel from the VIS image. Some pigments have characteristic colour changes.

Equipment

Camera	Nikon D810 (modified to full spectrum, UV-IR blocking filter removed)
Lens	Nikon AF NIKKOR 50 mm
Filters	CHSOS Robertina filters for VIS and UV, B+W 093 for IR
Light sources	Nikon speedlight V860ii for VIS and IRR CHOS Fabrizio UV-light for UVL and UVR
Software	Adobe Photoshop, Adobe Camera Raw, Adobe Bridge, Nip2 with Bm-workspace
Standards	Calibrite Classic Mini McBeth color chart Spectralon© reflectance standards; 2, 50 and 99 % reflectance

Light sources

Irradiance profile of Nikon Speedlight V860ii measured at 100 cm distance with an Ocean Optics Flame spectrometer.

CHSOS Fabrizio UV-light measured at 100 cm distance with an Ocean Optics Flame spectrometer.

Raw data

Tif and jpg images are stored on the Swedish National Heritage Boards raw database Lida (L:) and available upon request.

References

1. Dyer, J., Verri, G. & Cupitt, J., 'Multispectral Imaging in Reflectance and Photo-induced Luminescence modes: a User Manual', 2013, Web publication/site, European CHARISMA Project, Online.
2. GitHub - BritishMuseum/bm-charisma: A nip2 workspace for technical imaging <https://github.com/BritishMuseum/bm-charisma> (2023-03-24)

Appendix 1 – VIS images of 14 fragments

Appendix 2 – Summary of captured images of 14 fragments (VIS, IRR, IRRFC, UVRFC, UVR, UVL)

Appendix 3 – VIS image of 25621 “Calendar with blue text”

Uidi aquam *ad passionem*

egredientem de templo a latere
dextero aevia q omnes ad quos pue
nit aqua ita salvi facti sunt

q dicunt aevia ae via. *Coficem*
ec est dies scilicet scilicet die. *scilicet*

Hec est clara dies clararu clara die
rum. nobile nobilium vigilanti di
adema dierum. *Coficem scilicet*

Salve festa dies toto venerabil

ma
eius. Quis infernum uicem q alia
tente. Ecce renascens celtari

g. A mundi. oia ex dno dona re
dite suo. *Salve. Namq; et i*
umphanti post crista tarcari

et a uoce laetima uili elania

*D*ominus noster ihesus christus qui in mundo
natus est et omne populum et omne
uoluntatem nostram in se habet et
omni uoce laetima uili elania

flore fuerunt. *S. L* egit; inferni
oppressis sup alia meantē laudant
rite deū. lux. polus. arua fretū. *S.*
si crucifix; erat d; ecce p oia r; gnat

Nobilitas anni mensis dec arma dierū
hoary splendor seripula pūcta fave. *S.*
pe sal mūda bone cōdico atq; redēpar

E qual' contos loel cū patre coeors.
quo supite mundul. pncipe pncipio. *S.*
ce uolunt; q enī cantū de corpore nati.

S. a caro q nati pculit acq; mox. *Sal.*
fuerit. exeqas pater f uice autrag. oib.
hrens mortis recer. dando saluicosep. *S.*

Qum rex glorie *honoru. A*
xpe infernum debellatu us in
tra rec q chaos angelicu auce

faciem eius portās pncipium
collere preciperet sanctor choi
qui tenebantur in moce cap

et a uoce laetima uili elania

Et cū spū tuo.

Agnus dei q̄ tollis. **III.**

Fiat hec cōmixtio
q̄ consecratio corporis et
sanguinis dñi nr̄i ih̄u xp̄i
oib; accipientib; salus me
tis q̄ corporis q̄ ad uitam
eternā capiendā prepa
ratio salutaris. **v. ocul**

Dñe ih̄u **calicē** q̄ in
xp̄e q̄ dixisti discipulis
tuus pacē meā do uobis
pacē relinquo uob; ne
respicias ad peccata mea
s; respice ad fidē sc̄e ecclie
tue. eā q; secundū tuam
uoluntatē pacificare
custodire regere q̄ coad
unare digneris. nos q; a
peccatorū uinculis liberi.
q̄ ab omni p̄turbatione
ualeam' esse securi. **S. i. d.**

Pax tecū. **v. d. n. x. t. cū. s. t.**

Pax xp̄i q̄ q̄ popl's dñe
ecclie maneat sep̄ nob̄e.

Dñe ih̄u xp̄e q̄ p̄b̄i:

Dñi sū dignus ut intres
sub tectū meū. s; saluum
me fac in tua m̄ia q̄ salu
eris p̄ assūptionē ueri corpo
ris q̄ sanguinis tui. ut n̄

ad iudiciū dāpnationis illud
sumā. s; te miserante sic
m̄ p̄piciabile in uitā et̄nā.

Ave. in et̄nū
celestē cib; caro x̄. sis m̄ sup
oīa q̄ inter oīa mei dulcedo.

Corp' dñi nr̄i
ih̄u x̄ cōsit mecum in om̄i
opere bono.

Ave in et̄nū sanguis x̄. m̄ sis
sup oīa dulcis.

Corp' q̄ sanguis dñi nr̄i ih̄u x̄.
custodiat me in uitā et̄nā.

Accipienti
m̄ indigno famulo tuo
corp' q̄ sanguinē tuū dñe ih̄u
xp̄e. cōcede ut ibi nulla rema
neat peccati macula. ubi cāta
intier̄ sacramenta.

Dñe ih̄u xp̄e q̄ ex uoluntate
p̄tis coopante sp̄e sc̄i gr̄a
p̄ mortē tuā mūdū redemisti
libera me p̄ hoc sac̄ sc̄m corpus
q̄ sanguinē tuū. q̄ fac me ut
p̄ oīa obedire mandatis q̄ a
te nūq̄ in p̄petuū separari.

Quod ore sūptim'
mente capiam'. q̄ de mune
tēporali fiat m̄ remedio sepien̄s.

Trio puerorū **Post nullam**
cantem'. **Benedicere.** **P̄ d̄ m̄ sc̄s.**

ne dimittat. **K. S. X.**

S cē michael.	oratio p nob.	S vies tū q' tū d's.	oratio.
O oīs scī angeli q' archangeli.	oratio.	S cā dei genitrix.	oratio p.
S cē iohannes baptista.	oratio.	S cē gabriel.	oratio.
O oīs scī patarce q' pphie.	oratio.	O oīs scī angeli q' archi.	oratio.
S cē petre.	oratio.	S cē abraham.	oratio.
S cē paulo.	oratio.	S cē isaac.	oratio.
S cē andrea.	oratio.	S cē iacob.	oratio.
S cē iacobe.	oratio.	O oīs scī patarce q' pphie.	oratio.
O oīs scī apli q' ex.	oratio.	S cē iohannes.	oratio.
S cē stephane.	oratio.	S cē iacobe.	oratio.
S cē line.	oratio.	S cē philippe.	oratio.
S cē clete.	oratio.	S cē bartholomee.	oratio.
S cē clement.	oratio.	O oīs scī apli q' ex.	oratio.
O oīs scī martires.	oratio.	O oīs scī discipuli dñi.	oratio.
S cē silvester.	oratio.	S cē laurenti.	oratio.
S cē leo.	oratio.	S cē vincenti.	oratio.
S cē hilari.	oratio.	S cē olaue.	oratio.
S cē uenanti.	oratio.	S cē thoma.	oratio.
O oīs scī cōfessores.	oratio.	S cē bochuunde.	oratio.
S cā maria magdalena.	oratio.	S cē eskille.	oratio.
S cā agatha.	oratio.	S cē pancrati.	oratio.
S cā agne.	oratio.	O oīs scī martires.	oratio.
S cā cecilia.	oratio.	O oīs scī innocentes.	oratio.
O mīl scē uirgines.	oratio.	S cē martini.	oratio.
O oīs scī.	oratio p nobis.	S cē nicholae.	oratio.
K yrie. ad fontē dōs.		S cē gregori.	oratio.
K yrie. p̄ p̄et. Kyrie.		S cē ambrosi.	oratio.
X p̄e audi nos. p̄ acer de cel.		S cē augustine.	oratio.
deus. miserere nob.		S cē ieronime.	oratio.
F ili redēptor mūdi d's. miser.		S cē benedictē.	oratio.
S ps scē d's. miserere nob.		O oīs scī cōfessores.	oratio.

o Anna in excelsis. Benedictus
qui natus in nomine domini o

anna in excelsis. **Collecte**

Sanc tus. sanc tus

anc tus dominus

sabbath pleui fact

terra glori a tua **anna**

in excelsis. **B**enedictus qui

ue ut in nomine domini

anna in excelsis.

Crede in unum dnm patre omnipotentē factore celi
et terre visibilium hominum et invisibilium et unum do
minū hūmānū filium et unigenitū ex patre
nātū ante omnia secula dnm de deo lumē de lumē
deū verū de deo vero genitū nō factū cōsub
stantiale patri p quē omnia facta sūt q̄ p̄t nos hoīes
et p̄t nr̄am salutē descendit de celis et incarnat
us est de spu scto remansit uirgine et hō factus est
ficus etia p nob. sub pontio pilato passus et
sepultus et resurrexit tertia die scdm scripturas
et ascendit in celum sedet ad dexteram patris et
uenerus est cū glā iudicare uiuos et mortuos tū regni
nō erit finis et i spm scdm dnm et unificatōe q̄ ex patre
et filio procedit q̄ cū patre et filio simul adoratur et
conglorificatur et cetera. Amen.

Ignati stant
sime pater p
xpm filium
mum nostrum. sup
rogamus ac petimus
accepta habeas et
huc do. huc uir
in huc sancta sc
habita. In primis q
de terminis pro eccl
sancta catholica quam
uisceribus custodire
regere dignens toto
terrarum una cum fam
no. Amen. Amen.

descendens: ut si quis ex ipso
manducaverit non moriatur.
Ego sum panis vivus: qui de
celo descendi. Si quis manduca
verit ex hoc pane: vivet in eter
num. Et panis quem ego dabo
caro mea est: pro mundi vita.

Amitte spiritum tuum et creata offerentia
Abundantia & renouabis faciem
terre. sit gloria domini secula. **ALLA. SCR.**

Accepe quod domine munus ob
latum. et dignanter
operare. ut quod mysterium a
gimus. pro effectibus celebem. **V.**
COMMUNIO Patrem meam do nobis
allā. patrem relinquo nobis allā. allā.

Sumentes domine post com
munionem celestia sacramenta
clementiam tuam: ut quod tem
poraliter egimus. eternis gau
diis consequamur. **V. dñm.**
PRÆ. S. INVOCATIO. S. P. S. D. M. REPL.
PER TOTUM Sicut in die. ORATIO

Domine quod domine. ut a nostris
membris carnales amo
ueat spiritus sanctus affectus. et
spiritualia nobis donata potenter
infundat. **V. Ite agnum aploz**
A diebus illis: Philippus
descendens in civitatem sa

marie. predicabat illis dominum. In
tendebant autem viri huius que
a philippo dicebantur: unanimi
ter audientes. & videntes signa
que faciebat. Multi enim eorum
qui habebant spiritum immundum:
clamantes voce magna exclamabant
Multi enim palam. & clausi. mi
ram sunt. Factum est ergo gaudi
um magnum. in illa civitate.

ALLA. X. Loquetantur uariis
linguis apud magnalia dei. ALLA
Veni sancte spiritus. secundum

Allā. **Conuocatis lucam.**
hic duodecim discipulis: dedit
illis uirtutem et potestatem super
omnia demonia. & ut languores
curarent. Et misit illos predica
re regnum dei: et sanare infirmos.
Et ait ad illos. Nichil uuleris
in uia. neque uirgam. neque peram:
neque panem. neque pecuniam. neque
duas tunicas habentes. Et in
quemcumque domum intrauerit:
ibi manete. et inde ne exeat. Et
quicumque non receperit uos. ex
euntes de civitate illa. etiā pulue
rem pedum uostro egerite. in testi
monium super illos. Egressi autem
circuibant per castella: euange

In cho
runt ob nam e i ro v.
mif tra adoret te d. 7 p. Orenf
Omipc sempiternc deus
q xpi filij tuu leata pas
sione nos reparas conserua
in nobis opa misericordie tue.
ut in eius celebritate miste
rii ppetua deuotione uiua
mus **De eundē Ad massam.**
Domine ne longe faci as
sursum tuum a me ad de
ensionem meam aspice libe
ra me in de o re leo in
a coru bus unicornum
humilitatem me am **ps** d
m's res in me quare me
liquisti **collecta**

Omipc sempiternc d's
qui humano generi
ad imitandum humilita
tis exemplum saluatorem
nr̄m carnē sumere 7 cru
cem subire fecisti. concede. qd
cete ppiauis: ut 7 paciencie
ipsius habere documenta.
7 resurrectionis osorcia me
reamur **De eundē Ad philipen**
Tres. hoc sentate in ses
uobis: qd et in xpo
ihu Qui cum in forma
di esset nō rapinam arbi
tratus est esse se equalem
deo: set semet ipm exman
uit formam serui accipi
ens In similitudine homi
nū factus: 7 habitu inuen
tus ut homo humiliatur
semet ipm factus obediens
usq; ad mortem: mortē au
tem crucis Propter qd 7 d's
exaltauit illum 7 donauit
illi nomen quod est sup
onīe nomen: ut in nomie

glia dñi in secula allā. *Secreta.*

Minera q̄s dñe oblata
sanctifica. et corda n̄ra
s̄i sp̄c illustratione emunda. *psa*

Qui ascendes sup omnes saeclos.
Communicantes q̄ noctem sac̄

comumio **V**ltimo festivitatis die
duclat ih̄c qui in̄e uelunt summa
de uentre eius fluent aque uive. hoc
autem dixit de sp̄u quem adepturi
erant credentes in eum allā allā. *ps̄m*

Pā q̄s omnipotens d̄s. ut
sp̄c sanctus adueniens
maiestatem nobis filii tui man
festando clarificet. *ps̄m*

P *die sc̄o.*
ad missā
officium
paritatis
dñi reple
uit orbem
terrarum
allā. 7

hoc qd̄ conuert omnia terram
habet uons allā. allā. allā. *ps̄m*
Non
quid dixit es in nobis a teplo
et fugiunt qui oderunt eum a face ei.

Ceus qui hodierna *collā.*
die corda fidelium s̄i sp̄c

illustratione coruisti. da nobis
in eodem sp̄u recta sapere. et de
eius semp̄ sancta consolatione
gaudere. *ps̄m. lio actum ap̄lōr.*

In dieb; istis **D**ominus comple
rentur dies pentecostes: erant
omnes discipuli pariter in eode
loco. Et factus est repente de
celo sonus tamquam aduemen
tis sp̄c uehementis: et repleuit
totam domum ubi erant sedentes.

Et apparuerunt illis disparte
lingue tamquam ignis: sedite
supra singulos eorū. Et repleti
sunt omnes spiritu sancto: et
reperunt loqui uariis linguis
prout sp̄c sanctus dabat eloqui
illis. Erant autem in iherusa
lem habitantes iuri religiosi: *iudei.*

ex omni natione que sub celo
est. Facta autem hac uoce con
uenit multitudo et mente cō
fusa est: qm̄ audiebant unus
quisq; linguam suam. illos lo
quentes. Suscepant autem
omnes: q̄ mirabantur dicentes.

Nonne ecce omnes isti qui lo
untur galylei sunt: Et quom̄
nos audiuimus unusquisq; lin

quam.

III.

ER. OO
 NIA SE
 CVLAS
 ACLOZ
 DOMI

Et cum spiritu tuo. **S**ursu
 corda. **H**abemus ad do
 minum. **G**ratias agamus
 domino deo nostro. **D**ignu
 et iustum est.

ere dig
 num et
 iustum
 est equi

um et salutare. nos tibi se
 per et ubiq; gratias agere
 domine sancte pater omni
 potens eterne deus. per cri
 stum dominum nostrum.

Per quem male
 tuam laudant a
 rant domination
 unt potestates. Ce
 uirtutes ac beata
 socia exultatione
 brant. Cum quib
 nostras uoces up
 ti iubeas deprec
 supplici confessio
 tes. **S**anctus. **S**c
 dominus d's saba
 ni sunt celi et terra
 tua osanna in ex
 neditus qui ueni
 mine d'ni osanna
 sis. **E**t ideo cum
 et archangelis cu

minationibus. cuiq;
tia celestis exercitus
gle tue animus si
ucentes. S. S. S. S.

ua accepta habeas
icas hec dona. hec
hec sancta sacrificia
In primis que t' offe
ro ecclia tua sancta
a quam pacificare
e adunare et regere dig
o orbe terrarum una
nulo tuo papa nro.
tistate nro. et regere
et omnib; orthodox
catholice et aplice fidi

Memento domine famuloz
famularumq; tuarum. et
et omium circumstantium qz
tibi fidel cognita est. et nota de
uotio. pro quib; tibi offerim
uel qui t' offerunt hoc sacrifici
um laudis. pro se suisq; omib;
pro redemptione animarum
suarum. pro spe salutis et in
columitatis sue. tibiq; reddat
uota sua eterno deo uiuo et

Communicantes uero.
et memoriam uenerates
in primis gloriose semp uirgi
nis marie genitricis di et do
mini nri ihu xpi. sed et beato
rum apstorum ac martirum

Petri. Pauli. Andree. Iacobi.
Iohannis. Thome. Iacobi Phi
lippi. Bartholomei. Mathei. Si
monis. et Thadei. Iuliani. Cleci.
Clementis. Sixti. Corneli. Ci
priani. Laurentii. Crisogoni.
Iohannis. et papauli. Cosime
Damiani. et omium scoz
tuorum quorum meritis pre
cibusq; concedeas ut in omni
bus protectionis tue munia
mur auxilio. per eundem
christum dominum nrm.

Sicut de **h**enrici
Sicut de **h**enrici

Omnipotens deus qui beatus henricus
illius tui atque pontificis
gloriosi triumphum largitus es pal-
mia eius quibus unitis et patribus gra-
tia nobis largiaris et gloriam

Sicut deus qui beatus henricus
suffragantibus meritis
ad nostrae salutis auxilium puen-
ire concedere

Sicut deus qui beatus henricus
familiam tuam misericordibus lacis eius quibus
intuente nos refouere ausus so-
lemniter celebramus

Omnipotens deus qui gloria beatus wilhelmus
in confessoris tui atque pontificis
exempla humilitatis nobis
iter ostendere uoluit. precibus fa-
miliariter imitatus respice
et inter quos uenerandus pater
auterellit ipius intuitu sine

an's vitalibus
phis **C**onplu
bati wilhelmus
tor bone no
dummeto tu
uia ueritas
ficatis meti
amur

Deus qui
consilio
ethnudi co
pontificis po
deuocasti et
miraculis
bis famulis
in melius
phis. et ab om-
nibus ptegan

Bcati et
tui at
due misericordie
placeat obla-
ant ad salutem
entes u

tenebrae mentis do
molum **U**rgo pe
nis in atrita rotas
patibulo presentatur si
munita fidei signatu
lo genui flectit orat i
ta gravitate populo

Et confirmes spera
tuos et honore vobis
reliquis sigibor vni
virtute minims st
em deus hanc ligno
rum idu frange fal
minis **D**ox comple

tur mox unctura
rotaru dissoluitur
altans motus e
sura populi pa s te
ritur pars bapt hmi
susceptura virginu
conungitur **F**ide fi

des occultata regis
uxor emicat deos
regis detestata xpm
regem predicat toi
tis manibus ornata
sue costati dimicat

Ocollari du tube
tur caput offert gla
dia petit sibi suffra
getur virginis oro
ex defectu ne fradet
palme sue pmo **H**u
et nos in **ymptus**

Presens dies ex
pedatur in eis
predominant utus
ulatur i ore landa
ni si gestos teneat
tims et mmi **U**erbo
vite roboratus pilit
porphyrus cu dnce

pra quis. ut qui eius
dem virginis humi
litas et gaudios
quibus elizabet vi
sitavit sollempnia
celebramus in eor
memoria et gaudi
is iugiter manea
mus. *perinde certe q
hinc omnia sunt que
in notula eiusde. In
assumptio marie virg*
Tu omnibus requiem
quesivi et in here
ditate dñi morabor
tunc p̄cepit et dixit
michi creator dñi
et qui creavit me
requiem in taber
naculo meo. *Deo
gratias **ymnus.***

O qua glorifica
lute chorustas siq̄is
dauntur regia proles
sublimis residens vir
go mari a supra celi
genas. *Theris omnes*
Cus. *uigines ma
ter hancit angelo
e domo pectoris*

9635_1_nip2_VIS.jpeg

9635_1_nip2_IRR.jpeg

9635_1_nip2_IRRFC.jpeg

9635_1_nip2_UVRFC.jpeg

9635_1_nip2_UVR.jpeg

9635_1_nip2_UVL.jpeg

9635_2_nip2_VIS.jpeg

9635_2_nip2_IRR.jpeg

9635_2_nip2_IRRFC.jpeg

9635_2_nip2_UVRFC.jpeg

9635_2_nip2_UVR.jpeg

9635_2_nip2_UVL.jpeg

9635_streck_nip2_VIS.jpeg

9635_streck_nip2_IRR.jpeg

9635_streck_nip2_IRRFC.jpeg

9635_streck_nip2_UVRFC.jpeg

9635_streck_nip2_UVR.jpeg

9635_streck_nip2_UVL.jpeg

26692_nip2_VIS.jpeg

26692_nip2_IRR.jpeg

26692_nip2_IRRFC_aligned.jpeg

26692_nip2_UVRFC_aligned.jpeg

26692_nip2_UVL.jpeg

26692j_nip2_VIS.jpeg

26692j_nip2_IRR.jpeg

26692j_nip2_IRRFC.jpeg

26692j_nip2_UVRFC.jpeg

26692j_nip2_UVL.jpeg

3814_nip2_VIS.jpeg

3814_nip2_IRR.jpeg

3814_nip2_IRRFC.jpeg

3814_nip2_UVRFC.jpeg

3814_nip2_UVL.jpeg

6638_nip2_VIS.jpeg

6638_nip2_IRR.jpeg

6638_nip2_IRRFC.jpeg

6638_nip2_UVRFC.jpeg

6638_nip2_UVR.jpeg

6638_nip2_UVL.jpeg

10156_nip2_VIS.jpeg

10156_nip2_IRR.jpeg

10156_nip2_IRRFC_aligned.jpeg

10156_nip2_UVRFC_aligned.jpeg

10156_nip2_UVL.jpeg

10411_nip2_VIS.jpeg

10411_nip2_IRR830.jpeg

10411_nip2_IRRFC830_aligned.jpeg

10411_nip2_UVRF830.jpeg

10411_nip2_UVL.jpeg

7285_id1_s1_nip2_VIS.jpeg

7285_id1_s1_nip2_IRR.jpeg

7285_id1_s1_nip2_IRRFC.jpeg

7285_id1_s1_nip2_UVRFC.jpeg

7285_id1_s1_nip2_UVR.jpeg

7285_id1_s1_nip2_UVL.jpeg

7285_id4_s2_nip2_VIS.jpeg

7285_id4_s2_nip2_IRR.jpeg

7285_id4_s2_nip2_IRRFC.jpeg

7285_id4_s2_nip2_UVRFC.jpeg

7285_id4_s2_nip2_UVL.jpeg

9451_nip2_VIS.jpeg

9451_nip2_IRR.jpeg

9451_nip2_IRRFC.jpeg

9451_nip2_UVRFC.jpeg

9451_nip2_UVR.jpeg

9451_nip2_UVL.jpeg

4602p_nip2_VIS.jpeg

4602p_nip2_IRR.jpeg

4602p_nip2_IRRFC.jpeg

4602p_nip2_UVRFC.jpeg

4602p_nip2_UVR.jpeg

4602p_nip2_UVL.jpeg

4602o_nip2_VIS.jpeg

4602o_nip2_IRR.jpeg

4602o_nip2_IRRFC.jpeg

4602o_nip2_UVRFC.jpeg

4602o_nip2_UVR.jpeg

4602o_nip2_UVL.jpeg

iiii	MONAS	Domini confessoris. p. l.
v	A viii	Sixti pape.
vi	B vii	Donati oris.
vii	C vi	Cyriaci mris.
viii	D v	
ix	E iiii	Laurencij archid. i or.
x	F iii	Augusti nepa
xi	G ii	pma fugat
xii	A idus	de fine seda.
xiii	B xviii	Transit in
xiiii	C xvii	Augusto
xv	D xvi	de terris
xvi	E xvi	regia ugo.
xvii	F xv	
xviii	G xiiii	
xix	A xiii	
xx	B xii	
xxi	C xi	
xxii	D x	
xxiii	E viii	
xxiiii	F vii	
xxv	G vi	
xxvi	A v	
xxvii	B iiii	
xxviii	C iii	
xxix	D ii	
xxx	E i	

f simple
 f s
 orem
 l m

vigla

Tyburcij oris. meff
 Hippoliti oris. f s
 Assumptio S marie. f. totu
 Oct S laurencij. f s
 Agapiti or. Solivurgue. orem

Signum uirg
 nis p eo qd d
 genitrix filioru
 genuit uirga
 totu permanit
 VIRGO

Octaua Sæe marie. f simple
 Bartholomea apti. f. Duple f
 Eodonic. regf & confessor

Hermetis oris. augustini
 Decollatio Sei Iohis. s f
 Felcis & adaueti. oris. l m v eg

